

THE EDUCATIONAL VALUE OF TEACHING ANVAR ABIDJON'S POEMS IN PRIMARY GRADES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10890924>

Annotation: This article discusses the educational importance of teaching the creativity of contemporary children's poets and writers in expanding the worldview of elementary school students and developing reading culture among them. In particular, samples of Anvar Obidjon's work were taken and analyzed.

Key words: children's literature, methods, artistic speech, text analysis.

I.I. Arkin, an expert who has been dealing with the problems of reading among young people for a long time and the theoretical and practical issues of determining the aesthetic taste of students, about the formation of high artistic taste in primary school students as early as possible: "If children, starting from the first grade, it is taught to read and accept literary works as an art phenomenon, to measure them by the criteria of artistry, to distinguish genuine art from fakes, if it is engaged with literature throughout the school years, following its integrity and systematicity, 5th graders are receptive to high art works. Unfortunately, the earlier we reach children with a genius artist, the faster the children will grow as readers, and therefore spiritually. We still can't understand what gives - his comments are worthy of attention.

According to the requirements of the new curriculum for primary education, in the 3rd grade, "formation of the ability of the student to read a certain text consciously, that is, with understanding; in this, to read expressively, observing the tone, stops, and punctuation of the words and sentences in the text, memorizing 5-6 poems; read and retell the text; getting answers to questions about the work in the textbook and by the teacher; determining the scope of the work; comparing the title with the main idea in the work; teaching students to express an opinion about the work; dividing the work into parts; express an opinion about the heroes who participated in it, compare and give a simple description; proving what is good and what is bad; grouping works according to the scope of the subject; it is required to teach to interpret the meaning of the used words, draw the child's attention to artistic expressions, images and include them in the student's speech. To fulfill these requirements, we recommend studying the poem "Khotira Whirdobi" in small groups.

The growth levels of students' speech are determined. Insufficient indicators are worked on in cooperation with parents. These indicators can be defined as follows:

1. Small text reading speed...
2. The number of correct answers to the text questions...
3. Student's connected speech (forms of oral speech are controlled).
4. The student's level of retelling and explaining the content of a certain text.
5. The level of reading... (*the number of independently read literary works; the ability to express one's independent opinion about the work; the level of being able to relate to the events and characters of the work*).

If the students' capabilities or activities do not meet any of the specified levels, they should work together to raise this indicator by means of auxiliary tasks. Only then will the effectiveness of education be achieved.

In this method, students in the class are divided into small groups of five or six people. Each of the members of the small group will have their own number. The members of the groups begin the analysis of the eight-line poem based on the cards given to them. Each small group performs the tasks on the cards independently, that is, they prepare their answers according to the tasks on the cards.

After the preparation of all small groups, the presentation begins. Then the teacher says some number, for example, "4". Participant number 4 of each group presents the answers of his group. Doing so eliminates the risk of the best student in small groups becoming the presenter every time. In order not to spend a lot of time listening to a small group's answer to the eight verses, each group is asked to answer two questions. It is a method that is effective in that it is aimed at activating the students of the same number in other groups to answer the question, whichever number the student answers.

Undoubtedly, talented poet Anvar Obidjon is one of those who raised the Uzbek poetry of the 20th-21st century to the heights. It is clearly defined in the curriculum and programs that various works created by the poet should be taught organically and continuously at the educational stages.

It has always been a demand to teach the life and work of the People's Poet of Uzbekistan, winner of the "Shuhrat" medal, the life and work of Anvar Obidjon, who are the owners of our future, in the educational process. After all, teaching the poems of the poet given in the programs and textbooks in effective ways, based on the requirements of the time, serves to enrich the spirituality of

students, to form their independent thinking, to increase their speech and worldview, and to increase their love for fiction.

Anvar Obidjon's life activity, his works, poems have a great educational power. The transfer of such an impressive power to the hearts of students, taking a firm place in their hearts, can be a worthy contribution to their education as a perfect person in all respects.

Anvar Obidjon's works are a rare monument in the history of our literature that can serve to enrich the spirituality of our students and develop their literary taste. Masterly and effective use of this opportunity is one of the urgent tasks facing the education system.

Teaching the life and work of a poet or writer at the educational stages includes certain didactic and educational goals. By studying examples of works of famous writers, students get acquainted with works of art. With its power of influence, they enter the world of beauty and sophistication. They learn to understand the imagery characteristic of a work of art, the meanings behind figurative expression. They learn to understand the content of human experiences and to feel the feelings of the creator in their hearts. At this moment, through the works created by each artist, they get to know him, enter the world of the soul, and understand the essence of the poet's thoughts. Word artists are embodied in the eyes of the reader with a unique, unique image. A number of folk poets such as A.Obidjon, E.Vokhidov, A.Oripov, M.Yusuf become examples and lessons for students due to the feeling and understanding of the poet's image, mental world, joys and sorrows of his works. Rather than long biographies of such creators, artistic works find their way to the hearts of readers faster and have an aesthetic effect.

The following information can be presented at the exhibition or presentation, giving information about the works of Anvar Obidjon.

"Clown boy" (1980), "Olovjan and his friends" (1983), "Bahram's stories" (1984), "Hey, bright world" (1983), "Ketmagil" (1985), "Malaria" (1985), "Very Interesting Event" (1987), "Golden Hearted Autoboy" (1988), "Dahshatli Meshpolvon" (1990) and other poetry and prose books were published. Anvar Obidjon in recent years "Ramadan and Gulmat Hangoma" (1992), "Meshpolvan's Battles" (1994), "Alisher ila Husain or Three Wise Men and Thieves" (1996), "Parrot", "Topsang He also created short stories, poems and epics like "hay-hay...". He was awarded the title of "People's Poet of Uzbekistan" (1998).

To read and analyze:

Ota o'giti - Father's son.

*Har bitta so'z – suvdek aziz,
Har bitta so'z – nondek uvol.
Til boyligin bog' deb bilsak,
Har bitta so'z – bitta nihol.*

*Every word is as dear as water.
Every word is like bread.
If we consider language as a garden,
Each word is one sprout.*

Through these verses, the 4th grade student tries to pay attention to his speech and acquire the manners of speaking. There is a saying in our people: "A child is dear, manners are dearer than him." It is at the heart of this wisdom that we are talking about children whose behavior and behavior are decorated with good manners. Anvar Obidjon also says this in the second stanza of the poem, wanting the young generation to have perfect qualities:

To waste a word
We must have plucked a sapling.
Gradually, the father inherits
It is to destroy the garden. That is, wasting words is like destroying a tree, a treasure inherited from ancestors.

My child, if you go to a foreign country,
What do you say, they say.
What nationality are you?

They say speak your mother tongue. Through this paragraph, children will learn that the face of each nation is its mother tongue. At this point, it is necessary to ask the children which foreign languages they know.

*Shunda mening qutlug' tilim –
Navoiyning she'ri, degil.
Yurtim – Ulug'begu Bobur,
Amir Temur yeri, degil.*

*Then my welcome language -
Not Navoi's poem.
My country is Ulugbegu Babur,
It is not the land of Amir Temur.*

In this paragraph, the poet looks at the history of our language and spirituality. He mentions the name of our great scholars. The last stanza of the poem especially gives the reader a sense of infinite pride.

*Obro'yingni baland tutmoq,
E bolam, o'z qo'lingdadir.
Sening olamdagi narxing
Vatan, millat, tilingdadir.*

*To keep your reputation high,
My child, it is in your hands.
Your price in the world
Homeland, nation, is in your language.*

We discussed the importance of teaching Anvar Obidjon's poems in primary classes. Teaching the children's works of Uzbek and world literature to the younger generation is the demand of the times. Therefore, it is one of the important pedagogical problems to teach the works created by creators who have earned the respect and love of our people in the educational stages.

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